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The Impact of Psychological Factors on Consumer Green Purchase Behaviour: A Study of #NoStrawMovement Campaign in KFC Greater Jakarta

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Abstract

Plastic pollution is one of the most concerning issues presently and Indonesia is the second largest plastic waste producer in the world. A substantial part of the plastic waste comes from non-degradable plastic straws. This research intends to seek whether consumers' psychological factors have an impact on their green purchasing behavior with a case study of #NoStrawMovement in KFC Indonesia. The research has been carried out on 153 consumers. The outcome signified that all indicators of psychological factors do have an impact on consumers' green purchasing behavior. Perceived knowledge about sustainability issues, spirituality, drive for environmental responsibility and perceived marketplace influence are the decisive factors affecting consumers' green purchase behavior. It is revealed that psychological factors impact consumers' green purchase behavior by 51.6%. The result of the research will be worthwhile for KFC Indonesia to further revamp the effectiveness of the movement and for the government to establish a policy that supports green purchasing behavior. Advocating green purchasing behavior within society could aid in alleviating the damage that has been previously caused to the environment.

Keywords: Psychological Factors, Perceived Knowledge about Sustainability Issues, Spirituality, Drive for Environmental Responsibility, Perceived Marketplace Influence, Perceived Consumer Effectiveness, Attitude towards Sustainability Purchasing, Consumers' Green Purchase Behavior

1. Introduction

Currently the earth faces incoming danger from various environmental issues. These issues are caused by the actions of humans. These deeds in the end produce pollutions that endangered the world we live in. Plastic pollution is one of the major concerns that exist presently. Globally, around 1.3 billion tons of trash have dumped the ocean annually and the majority of it is plastics that will take decades, centuries or even a millennium to be degraded (Lehnardt, 2017). The examples previously stated are only the tip of the iceberg and the rest of it are more or at the least as horrifying as these ones. Indonesia is the second biggest producer of plastic trash in the

world with a total of 3.2 million tons out of 64 million tons of total trash per year and Indonesians use about 93 million plastic straws per day (Puspita, 2018; Arifah, 2018). These horrendous facts and news related to these, encourage an individual named Swietenia Puspa Lestari, leader of Yayasan Penyelam Lestari Indonesia, to initiate an organization named Divers Clean Action (DCA) in 2015 that focuses on marine debris issues (Divers Clean Action, 2018). She then started the #NoStrawMovement back in May 2017 hand in hand with PT. Fast Food Indonesia that operates KFC marine Indonesia, a franchised fast-food chain restaurant from the United States of America (Broekema, 2018). KFC Indonesia became the first multinational company in Indonesia that started implementing this movement in just several stores then from there they implement it in all their available stores across Indonesia. The movement was intended to avoid the usage of plastic straws and to get the consumers to be involved in this green practice whilst attempting to convert their usual purchase behavior to green purchase behavior. In spite of this, KFC Indonesia still provides plastic straws if their consumers ask for it (Alicia, 2018). This has already been a case for several previous studies regarding green purchase behavior, essentially there is a gap between an individual's attitude and behavior labelled as green attitude- behavior gap or green purchasing inconsistency (Joshi & Rahman, 2015). In a nutshell, this research will analyze the impact of psychological factors towards consumers' green purchase behavior.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Psychological Factors (PF)

As asserted by (Dima, 2013), PF are factors concerning psychology that is related to how it motivates one's actions. The factors in this case are: Drive for Environmental Responsibility (DER): This is related to the dedication an individual has to protect and improve the environment (Ekasari, 2018; Kumar & Ghodeswar, 2015). When an individual chooses to participate in #NoStrawMovement, this action is also a part of being responsible to the environment.

Spirituality (S): A process of seeking things that an individual holds sacred in their life as well as holding on to their beliefs and principles (Okpalaenwe, 2016; Nelson, 2009). There are different beliefs and philosophies for each individual. Partaking in #NoStrawMovement for some may bring them joy and for others, it may seem as a selfless act that eventually will lead the individual to the belief that this little act of protecting the environment could change a person to be a better version of themselves.

Perceived Consumer Effectiveness (PCE): The perceived impact by an individual to the environment through a particular action (Hanss & Doran, 2019; Yahya, et al., 2013). Part of the society views the deed of not using plastic straws as something that is a step towards the ultimate goal of eventually discarding any plastic made products although for some, this feat may just be some futile movement considering the fact that #NoStrawMovement is an act that can only be fully accomplished if the society participates as a whole.

Attitude towards Sustainable Purchasing (ASP): The cognitive appraisal of an individual towards the act of green purchasing (Joshi & Rahman, 2019; Lee, et al., 2014). For a fact, #NoStrawMovement in reality is very beneficial to the environment and it is not hard to do. However, not all individuals think alike.

Perceived Marketplace Influence (PMI): The impact on other consumers from the perspective of an individual through participating in #NoStrawMovement (Gani, et al., 2017; Leary & Vann, 2016).

Perceived Knowledge about Sustainability Issues (PKSI): The knowledge comprehended by an individual in relation to environmental problems (Vicente-Molina, et al., 2013; Joshi & Rahman, 2017; (Wang, et al., 2014). Environmental related problems have been increasing as days go by, society knows about these problems but some just do not know how imminent the danger really is. **H1:** Psychological Factors impact consumers' green purchase behavior.

2.2 Consumers' Green Purchase Behavior (CGPB)

GCPB is the act of buying and consuming products that have slight to zero impact to the environment (Onel, 2016). In other words, the behavior of consumers to purchase green products. According to D'ames, (2014) and Yan & Y azdanifard (2014) these green products are the products that do not pollute the earth and leave negligible carbon foot prints such as stainless- steel drink bottles, reusable coffee cups, biodegradable waste bags and many more. CGPB generally can be referred to as green buying behavior, environmentally responsible purchase behavior, and pro-environmental purchase behavior (Tan & Lau, 2011). As previously stated in chapter 1, there is a gap found in most studies related to green purchase behavior labelled as green attitude-behaviour gap or green purchasing inconsistency. This particular gap is caused by the weak relationship between the attitude of a consumer and their behavior. This happens when a consumer has a positive attitude towards buying green products however the reality says otherwise (Joshi & Rahman, 2015).

3. Research Method

This research implements a causal study. The targeted sample is the consumers of KFC Greater Jakarta (Jabodetabek) within the past year (2018 - 2019). A survey through online questionnaires with a total of 23 questions were distributed to 189 respondents. 153 out of 189 are accepted and the rest got filtered out as they did not meet the desired requirements. The questionnaire uses a five-point Likert scale from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree.' This type of scale is termed as a psychometric scale that was used to assess the impact of consumers' psychological factors on their green purchase behaviour. The data can be used after passing validity, reliability, and single linear regression analysis.

3.1 Research Model

Figure 1: Research Model

4. Discussion

Characteristics		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	78	51
	Female	75	49
Age	< 17	13	8
	17-24	61	40
	25-34	30	20
	35-44	18	12
	≥ 45	31	20
Occupation	Student	62	41
	Entrepreneur	39	25
	Employee	31	20
	Professional	15	10
	Others	6	4
Monthly Income (IDR)	<3.900.000	44	29
	3.900.000 - 5.000.000	30	20
	5.000.001 - 10.000.000	34	22
	> 10.000.001	45	29

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Table 1 above shows the overall demographic respondents. It shows that there were 78 males and 75 females that participated in this study. Most of them (40%) were from 17 to 24 years old. The majority of the respondents (41%) had an occupation as student and most of them have a monthly income under IDR 3.900.000 or above IDR 10.000.001.

4.1 Validity and Reliability Analysis

The validity test goes through Pearson correlation coefficient. After testing, all items are found valid since r-count is bigger than r-table 0.1587 ($df=151$, $n=153$), with a significance level of 0.05. While the reliability test goes through Cronbach's Alpha was used to examine the reliability of the study to make sure that it is consistent.

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Total Items
Psychological Factors (PF)	0.948	20
Consumers' Green Purchase Behavior (CGPB)	0.861	3

Table 2: Reliability Test Result

As shown in Table 2, the reliability coefficients of all items were above 0.80 and considered good.

4.2 Single Linear Regression Analysis

Based on the regression analysis results, the regression model of this study is as follows:

$$Y (CGPB) = -2.042 + 0.160 (PF)$$

4.5 Findings

The study is revolved around how PF may have an impact on CGPB. Through several tests, it is proven that PF does have an impact on CGPB by 51.6%. Thus, approving H1₁ and the findings of this study is fundamentally in accordance with Joshi & Rahman (2019) although, not particularly with the exact same results.

Surprisingly, PKSI is the most significant determinant of CGPB in contrast to the other five. This may have been a result of how limited knowledge regarding sustainability issues affects consumers buying green products. Consumers are prone to consume more environmentally harmful products when they are unaware of the consequences of how their buying behavior may impact the environment. This implies that when consumers do know the impact of plastic straws on the environment, they will be more likely to support and participate in #NoStrawMovement while in the process, altering their purchase behavior into green purchase behavior.

Additionally, S also plays a strong role in affecting CGPB only second to PKSI. This finding corresponds to the study by Chairy (2012), indicating that when consumers believe in an eco-friendly lifestyle, they will act accordingly to the belief. Consumers with this belief will support and participate in #NoStrawMovement.

This study emphasizes that DER is one of the most critical predictors, supporting Kumar & Ghodeswar (2015). Supposedly, the commitment to be responsible to the environment will lead consumers to support and participate in #NoStrawMovement and eventually encourage CGPB.

The study further revealed that PMI impacts CGPB significantly supplementing the research done by Leary & Vann (2016). Most respondents believe that one's conviction towards how an individual endeavor could impact another's behavior. In regards to participating in #NoStrawMovement, the act of participating could encourage others to do the same and more.

5. Conclusion

In short, the severity of plastic pollution in Indonesia has been magnified over the past few years. Indonesia became the biggest producer of plastic waste in the world by 2018. One of the biggest contributors to that is the usage of non-degradable plastic straws which has reached 93 million straws per day by 2018. Thus, to lessen the usage, DCA and KFC Indonesia start the #NoStrawMovement in 2017. Since then, it has been a policy at KFC Indonesia to not give straws to consumers even though some still criticize and still ask for straws. This problem is also supported by previous studies that found an attitude-behavior gap while investigating CGPB. Essentially, there is a discrepancy between consumers' positive attitudes towards buying green products and the actual purchasing decision. Therefore, this research is focused on finding the impact of PF on CGPB by using #NoStrawMovement in KFC Greater Jakarta as a case study.

From a total of 189 respondents, only 153 have consumed KFC Greater Jakarta's products over the past year and are aware of or have experienced #NoStrawMovement. After numerous tests, these are the results:

- PF is approved to have an impact on CGPB by 51.6%.
- 4 out of 6 indicators (PKSI, S, DER, and PMI) have strong impact and the remaining have moderate impact.

5.1 Managerial & Jurisdictional Implications

As previously stated, PF has an impact on CGPB. This indicates that teaching consumers regarding the issues revolving around the environment could be very beneficial for the consumers. As they start to learn and understand, consumers will be more drawn to change their purchasing behavior into green purchasing behavior. KFC Indonesia could teach more than just their present consumers, but also the younger generations by directly going to schools, as a part of CSR, as instilling knowledge and principle into kids is easier than changing the perspective or mindset of adults (Santi, 2016). Hence, younger generations can grow with the belief that using non-degradable plastics harms the environment and to restore it, starts from one's initiative to take action. The moment that this becomes

a habit for them, it will develop a sense of sustainable responsibility internally. Furthermore, the actions of those who are taught to be environmentally responsible may affect those who are not to act accordingly.

Aside from directly approaching consumers, indirectly reaching to consumers through social media proactively could be a great idea due to technological advancement. For instance, KFC Indonesia could post an advertisement on YouTube highlighting #NoStrawMovement. Additionally, KFC Indonesia should keep on posting updates concerning the movement hence, this may help bring more attention to its existence.

Lastly, making #NoStrawMovement installations in KFC's outlets at least once a month. These visually attracting installations made for consumers are made to educate them on why such a simple action of not using plastic straws can make such a vast difference on plastic pollution and to inform them on the current situation of the deteriorating environment.

KFC Indonesia has already reduced plastic straw waste by 45% in each outlet by the implementation of #NoStrawMovement. This result is already evident enough for the Indonesian government to create a policy similar or identical to the #NoStrawMovement for every F&B business in Indonesia. By applying this policy, Indonesia could decrease its plastic waste to a great extent. This change in society, if applied, will subtly force consumers to adapt to the change thus, altering their purchasing behavior into CGPB.

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